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MaaS – an enabling tool for Collaborative Traffic Management

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Abstract

Mobility as a Service (MaaS) is the integration of various forms of transport services into a single mobility service accessible on demand. For the user, MaaS offers added value through a single application to provide access to mobility, with a sole payment channel instead of multiple ticketing and payment operations. Although the main motivation behind MaaS is to provide better, digitally-enabled mobility services for the end-user, it has also many important wider benefits: MaaS has a clear potential to reduce the environmental impact of transport, like CO₂ emission, air pollution and congestion. MaaS aims at optimisation and more efficient use of the city transport system (and this builds an important link to traffic management and TM2.0) in a fully collaborative environment. MaaS can be the mobility sector's response to the circular economy trend – it builds on the existing services, but efficiently upgrading the ways they are combined, integrated and consumed.

Keywords: MaaS, TM2.0, Collaborative Traffic Management, mobility services

1. Introduction

While facing urbanization and therefore increase of car density in urban areas, cities not only face traditional challenges related to congestion, air quality and so on, but they also need to tackle new challenges, as they are losing the capability to forecast (and manage) the demand flow due to the influence of individual journey support systems. Consequently, they experience ineffective control actions and high volume of traffic in residential areas that leads to less safe streets.

The main reason behind this is the conflict of objectives between the city operators that aim to collective benefit by preserving average travel time, congestion, air quality and safety and the objectives of the private service providers that pursue individual benefit, suggesting the quickest/best route to destination for the single user.

A solution to overcome this conflict lays in sharing data and traffic management strategies by exploiting the connected traveller environment: users share data and travel needs while traffic control shares accurate traffic forecast the control strategy with vehicles while private service providers consider and support the control strategy shared by the cities, converging in a win-win scenario for both collective and individual mobility objectives.

The document is organized as follows: a first part describes Traffic Management 2.0 (TM2.0) and Mobility as a

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Service (MaaS) trends, while a second part is dedicated to the employment of MaaS as an enabler for fully collaborative Traffic Management. Finally, best practices and concluding highlights are closing the document.

2. Problem statement

With the rapid urbanization of the world, the concept of “smart cities” and the transformation of cities and road infrastructures into digital environments bring along an incredible opportunity for improving citizens’ mobility and welfare as well as fostering economic progress. Regional and municipal governments, as well as large public organizations and utilities, are striving to deliver higher levels of service to meet expectations for seamless and easy-to-use travel experiences and to put in place smart systems, solutions and strategies for mobility management. On the other hand, private actors and micro-mobility stakeholders invaded the market through offering a huge range of individual mobility services and solutions. We can therefore that we have in place a very complex ecosystem of traditional systems actuating strategies through traditional channels as well as individual mobility solutions for targeted information and a big amount of personal data.

However, there is still a gap between these two categories of stakeholders, between the city and its citizens, between who manages mobility and who finally makes use of mobility services that may lead to ineffective control of mobility. It often happens that community goals are in conflict with individual goals. The aim of this work is therefore to promote the optimization of intelligent systems and operations so as to orchestrate mobility into a balance dynamic system that satisfies the multi-modal, mixed mobility environment we find ourselves in. In order to achieve this, the paper suggests the integration of the concepts of MaaS and TM2.0 into a fully collaborative Network Mobility Management System.

3. Background

3.1. Mobility as a Service

Mobility as a Service (MaaS) is the integration of various forms of transport services into a single mobility service accessible on demand. For the user, MaaS offers added value through a single application to provide access to mobility, with a sole payment channel instead of multiple ticketing and payment operations. MaaS aims at providing an alternative to dependency on car ownership that may be seen as convenient, flexible, reliable and cheaper. The main building blocks of Mobility as a Service are: access to multimodal mobility services, single journey planning and ticketing options for the user, as well the provision of reliable and advanced travel information from the planning phase until the end of journey. As MaaS models become more mature, it is easy to predict various other value-added linked services (e.g. mobility-related integration of payment for parking or tourism or entertainment services consumed during the journey) that can be combined to the MaaS offering.

Although the main motivation behind MaaS is to provide better, digitally-enabled mobility services for the end-user, it has also many important wider benefits. A successful MaaS service brings new business opportunities and ways to organise and operate the various transport options as a seamless multimodal service. According to market evidence, MaaS has the potential to attract new customers and create demand for public transport where previously it did not exist. Therefore, MaaS has a clear potential to reduce the environmental impact of transport, like CO₂ emission, air pollution and congestion. MaaS aims at optimisation and more efficient use of the city transport system (and this builds an important link to traffic management and TM2.0). It aims to solve the mobility challenges of larger cities with soft measures and consequently reduce the need for public funding and subsidies in the transport sector. MaaS can be the mobility sector’s response to the call of the circular economy – it builds on the existing services, but upgrades the ways they are combined, integrated and consumed reducing inefficiencies in the system.

Around the world, there are currently various MaaS pilots, trials and business cases developed and launched. MaaS is challenging current players in the transport industry, urging them to rapidly position themselves in the reformed ecosystem and to find new partners and business models driven by optimization, resource efficiency and environmental responsibility – yet also meeting the growing needs of well-informed, digitally orientated and demanding customers and taking good care of social inclusion.

3.2. Traffic Management

Traffic Management finds its evolution with the TM2.0 concept/ platform. The TM2.0 platform aims to agree on common interfaces, principles and business models, which can facilitate the exchange of data and information between road vehicles and Traffic Management and Control Centres. The goal is to improve the total value chain for consistent traffic management and mobility services while avoiding conflicting guidance information on the road and in vehicles.

TM1.0 (Traditional Traffic Management): The Road Operator or Public Authority has traditionally been measuring the traffic and then, based on these measurements, tried to influence traffic via road signs and announcements. The Service Providers on the other hand were better placed to guide the traffic.

TM2.0 aims to close this loop and facilitate interactive traffic management. The Road Operator sends its Traffic Management Plans as these are decided by the Public Authorities to the Service Providers operating in the area, who then send tailor-made information to their customers with regards to routing provided via the in-car navigation device.

Closing this loop requires the coherence of:

- **Traffic management plans** provided by road authorities with
- **Dynamic traffic information** provided by traffic service providers with
- **Guidance** provided by navigation service providers

The TM2.0 Process:

- Collect data from all available sources feeding into the traffic management
- Data is fed into the statistics and modelling exercises performed by the Public Authorities when managing traffic. This is where we go into data processing
- Implementation of traffic management under the concept of TM 2.0 involves all means of information transmitters working towards informing and guiding the driver. All show the same information and follow

the coherence principle.

In TM 2.0 Service Providers do not compete on the information but on its quality and on how to best route customers while taking the priorities of public authorities into account. In exchange, the public authorities open their information on their traffic management plans and measures to all cooperating Service Providers. TM 2.0 provides an informed view of the road network that leads to optimization of Traffic Management.

4. MaaS as an enabler of Traffic Management

4.1. How can MaaS support TM

Traffic Management is based on a number of core functions:

Monitoring and Detecting: Accidents/Incidents, Road, Tunnel, Bridge Closures. Congestion

Defining and Executing: Road Works, De-Icing

Defining and Enforcing: Traffic Regulations

Influencing: Travel Route & Departure Time (Network Optimisation)

Defining and Executing: Traffic Management Plans/Strategies

Mobility as a Service is also based on a core set of functions and processes:

Journey Planning → Booking → Payment → Execution of the Journey.

There are many areas of potential collaboration between TM2.0 and MaaS in which the execution of the defined functions can support each other's systems, notably:

TM Travel and Route Info <> MaaS Journey Planning: Fact based journey planning – providing a trip offer integrating all information related to network status, for an effective trip planning across the network, ensuring a time-effective and cost-effective travel experience since the pre-trip phase.

TM Travel and Route Info <> MaaS Execution of the Journey: Always offering to the traveller up-to-date preference-based options during trip in order to improve time of reaction and efficiency of the travel itself. The feedback channel, containing real-time information of the trips enhances the accuracy of the real-time travel information.

TM Network Optimisation <> MaaS Journey Planning: Providing a trip offer integrating all information related to network status, for an effective trip planning across the network, ensuring a time-effective and cost-effective travel experience since the pre-trip phase. The TM should also propose specific recommendations (measures) in case of incidents or emergencies that will be reflected in the journey planning. Vice-versa, intention OD matrix derived from journey planning can be an input for traffic management strategies applied to reach equilibrium across the road network.

TM Network Optimisation <> MaaS Execution of the Journey: Always offering to the traveler up-to-date preference-based options during trip in order to improve time of reaction and efficiency of the travel itself. The feedback channel, containing real-time information of the trips has an impact on the decision making at traffic management side, enabling a real-time reaction to demand spread across the road network. At the same time, control strategies can be actuated through the MaaS offering with the final objective to incentive modal shift (also in case of incidents or emergencies).

The MaaS concept can institute a new sphere in traffic management, where traffic optimization measures and advanced services for the end-user can also be enabled by mobility service, for a fully collaborative traffic management, where the connected user is completely integrated in the management loop.

In the traffic management data flow, the following key actors can be identified: content (=data) providers, transport authorities, transport service providers, traffic management operators, service providers, MaaS operators and travellers.

Therefore, in the future MaaS world, traffic managers will have access to more dynamic traffic data (e.g. travel time, speed, traffic flow etc.) from a range of vehicles and transport modes not just road traffic data from traffic

information service providers. Through the access to information about scheduled events by network operators and municipalities, traffic data services related to forecasted travel time estimation, forecasted level of services can be realised. All of above can enable traffic managers to implement interactive multimodal traffic management and implement traffic management measures to optimize the speed and direction of all vehicles and transport modes.

Furthermore, if capacity levels drop or rise within the transport network and as such cannot be solved by traffic management measures alone, MaaS operators could be used to channel travel demand into a different travel mode or modes to optimize the flows in the network.

As traffic managers increasingly use geo-fencing to control road traffic passing through designated parts of a network (i.e. residential/school areas, high polluting zones, hospital areas), MaaS operators can also enable the provision of geo-fencing by promoting sustainable modes to pass through such areas.

4.2. The evolution of the TM2.0 concept in the MaaS

The combination of these concepts together (TM2.0 and MaaS) will lead to an evolution of the TM2.0 vision (that we can name TM2.1), that stands for a new interactive concept for Traffic Management and Control, in which the travellers by using new technologies and sensors, become entirely part of the multimodal data supply chain. In addition, traffic management operators work together with the MaaS operators to optimize the transport road capacity through the implementation of common interactive transport management measures across all the available different transport layers. For example, based on the integration of live traffic flow and incident data, MaaS operators can provide journey options to travellers based on the real-time situation, not static information. The picture below represents this interaction among all the transport actors, where they cooperate to achieve common transport objectives.

For sure this concept represents a revolution in the way we move and we manage transportation, based on a simple thing: data and information sharing. This on one side will enable a new mobility which is smarter, greener, more comfortable and safer in answer to our societal challenges. On the other side, the digitalization of mobility could expose the citizens to new risks, related to cyber security and digital inclusion.

5. Best practices

5.1. MyCorridor

MyCorridor is a 3-year project, funded by the Horizon 2020 programme and its overall objective is to achieve sustainable travel in urban and interurban areas and across borders by replacing private vehicle ownership by private vehicle use. The project looks into connecting services from various service providers and providing the traveller with alternatives to replace their own vehicle trip with combined shared vehicles and multimodal transport solutions. The project is part of the Mobility as a Service (MaaS) concept that puts users at the core of transport services, offering them tailor-made mobility solutions based on their individual needs.

Pilot demonstration of MyCorridor involves an eco-system of interoperable MaaS Issuers, covering together a cross-border Pan-European Corridor going through Greece, Italy, Austria, Germany, Czech Republic and the

Netherlands. Each MaaS Issuer can operate one or more local or cross-border corridors that involve various typologies of mobile users. MyCorridor aims to be all-inclusive, and, as such, cover the needs of all types of travelers with varying profiles (needs and preferences). Basic user profiles – representing a significant share of the population - that will be supported during the Pilots of the project through the MyCorridor system are namely: 1. The “Commuter” 2. The “Tourist” 3. The “Businessman” 4. The “Spontaneous user” 5. The “Mobility-restricted” user (i.e. user with disabilities) 6. The “Low IT literacy user” (i.e. elderly user)

My Corridor aims to enable a paradigm shift for car users, by driving the “vehicle world” towards Mobility as a Service (MaaS): it aims to extend the Traffic Management 2.0 (TM2.0) at its borders by providing a solution that incorporates multi-modal, seamless, flexible, reliable, user-friendly, all inclusive, price-worthy and environmentally sustainable traveler move at cities and regions and most importantly across all Europe. However, the basis of My Corridor project is the TM 2.0 platform (i.e. as an enabler of MaaS), and therefore starting point are those mobility services related to the interactive traffic management envision of the “vehicle world”.

These mobility services are clustered in four basic operational fields, which are 1) Traffic management applications, 2) MaaS Multi-modal PT applications interfaces concerning the planning, booking, ticketing and the use of the mobility multi-modal services, 3) MaaS vehicle related applications, and 4) Horizontal (non mobility) services concerning the purchasing.

5.2. Socrates 2.0

The European project SOCRATES2.0, co-financed by the EC CEF program, eleven public and private organisations work together to develop novel interactive traffic management services. 3 types of services, will be tested by at least 9,000 users in the regions of Amsterdam, Antwerp, Copenhagen and Munich. The services include smart route advice in case of events, actual speed and lane advice and local warnings, route advise on environmental zones and road works. The pilots will take place in 2019 and 2020 within motorways, regional roads, urban-interurban and urban roads. Project aim to create more business opportunities for the private partners, a more cost-effective traffic management for the public authorities and better service for the road users.

Socrates 2.0 aims to achieve this through more advanced and extensive data sharing between all partners through the TM2.0 framework. Within the project service providers and road authorities will work together towards a common understanding of the current traffic conditions and the expected conditions. Based on that they plan to adapt to the current traffic situation in union and with a common goal, each deploying the tools that said them apart in the real world. Road authorities will deploy road side equipment to inform traffic on current conditions and rerouting alternatives and will also adapt network performance where possible through for example, changing Traffic Light Controllers settings. The service providers will reroute their customer where possible and needed according to the common set goal and understanding between service providers and road authorities resulting in one, common message, to their end user, the road users. By eliminating conflicted information to the road user and aiming for a common goal the capacity in the road network can be used in a more effective way benefiting every road user. This can only be done by extensive data and insight exchange through the TM2.0 framework.

Conclusion

This paper aims to explore areas where MaaS can support Traffic Management operations and shows that this revolutionary concept has a clear potential to reduce the environmental impact of transport, like CO2 emission, air pollution and congestion. Besides a theoretical introduction, it is also presented a hypothesis on how core functions of both MaaS and Traffic Management can interact, and finally Best Practices show how this fully collaborative approach is being already adopted and implemented.

In the same context, later, it will also be worth studying how information from other sources, e.g. from transport service providers (like Uber Movement data) and fleet managers, could be used in order to optimise the traffic flows and management in cities, through traffic management measures and advanced data-based urban and traffic planning methods.

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